

SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF PEDAGOGUE IN SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE OF SOCIETY

¹Kadirova Yakitjan Buvabaevna, ²Kadirova Khalima Buvabaevna

^{1,2} Associated professors, Tashkent state pedagogical university

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Abstract. *Today's globalization processes, scientific and technical progress, the need for an innovative society create many opportunities for young people. They are faced with vital requirements such as making quick decisions, forming innovative thinking, increasing intellectual potential, and being loyal to national and universal values. This creates a vital need for the formation of organizational competence, which is considered important for the needs of society. Also, the society is working to increase the social activity of pedagogues in their social and political life.*

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The concept of organizational competence is used to refer to a person's performance at a high level based on a creative approach to organizational activities, work, tasks and responsibilities. In this sense, the organizational competence of teachers is effective in the organization of organizational-pedagogical tasks, the educational process, extracurricular tasks, events, and the formation of lessons on an innovative basis, during the manifestation of creativity, initiative and responsibility in their pedagogical and professional activities, the teacher and the student, as well as the educational institution. activity in organizational issues is demonstrated [1, p. 6480-6487].

The combination of organizational competence is a combination of the concepts of organization and competence, and the word "competence" in the second part of this phrase means "I am achieving, I am worthy, I am worthy" and it is a specific state body (local self-government body) or an official with a law, charter or other document. defined powers, scope of rights and duties, knowledge and experience in one or another field [2, p. 116-120].

In this sense, organization of organizational issues at a high level in society, having high-potential organizers who solve organizational problems in each field, raising organizational competence to the level of culture in general is understood as a product of social development.

Entrepreneurial culture as a complex and diverse phenomenon paves the way for the description of the activity of a person in the way of understanding and changing nature, society and self, and its derivative, as well as the norm of the universal, integrated and comprehensive development of society and the individual. Organizational competence is an attempt to solve organizational issues based on high knowledge, skills and abilities to change the social situation.

Many scientific studies have been conducted on the issues of business culture, management culture, business ethics, corporate culture, professional activity. At the same time, several studies are being carried out in western countries to solve the problems of teachers' organizational competence. All this created an opportunity to turn to the scientific research of the phenomenon of organizational competence in order to clarify the resource factors of the professional activity of the teacher and the development of the educational institution [3, p. 41-42].

Organizational competence is considered to have specific characteristics of the component of personal culture. A teacher must be cultured, because for the effectiveness of any institution, the staff must have high morale. In the center of reforming society, its modernization and reforms, teachers-coaches perform the main function [4, p.59]. The social activity of pedagogues in the socio-political life of society is a process that is largely related to the level of their educational activity. After all, "the greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, the greatest poverty is ignorance!" Therefore, for all of us, acquiring modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need.

So, organizing is an activity aimed at changing the social environment, and in this process, the organizer is required to form strong knowledge and a broad worldview, as well as to develop deep thinking. Because organizational performance refers to how work is done [5, p. 11-12].

In order to understand the essence of the organizational competence of a modern pedagogue and educational institution, it is necessary to express the hierarchy of scientific meanings that form the basis of the concepts of this phenomenon [6, p. 1373-1377].

To organize and manage pedagogical processes in an educational institution on a scientific basis and to create a comfortable and healthy environment in the team, to know various modern forms and methods of management and their requirements, to be able to determine the factors influencing their development, to regularly study best practices and scientific and technical achievements, it is important to implement them in their activities, to be able to organize innovative activities in the process of organization, to be very precise, demanding and flexible. Therefore, a number of scholars interpret organizational competence and its specific characteristics in different ways. Organization is a choice that requires a specific art and skill, making decisions based on that choice or search and controlling its implementation [7, p. 82].

In the current conditions, one of the main factors of improving the activities of pedagogical staff and effectively organizing the educational process in educational institutions is determined by the organizational skills of pedagogues. In this, it is important to develop new mechanisms of organizational competence, to search for news, learn and build on them, to work on oneself regularly, and to use scientifically based information in the process of activity, to master the pedagogical, psychological and socio-economic foundations of organizational work.

In general, in the process of increasing the social activity of pedagogues in the socio-political life of the society, in the process of organizing and managing the activities of educational institutions, the organizing leader should know and follow the following tasks:

planning in advance for the implementation of the assigned tasks, choosing effective ways of doing things, bringing the activity of the educational institution to a higher level; to develop according to the content and essence of the defined tasks, to select quality personnel, to determine their professional potential and level of training;

organization of the educational process on a scientific basis, increasing the efficiency by organizing the training and retraining of pedagogical staff;

providing the educational institution with material-technical and modern scientific-methodical manuals and textbooks;

advanced pedagogical experiences and effective and purposeful use of modern information and communication technologies and the study of pedagogical conditions. Therefore, it is necessary for the organizer to be able to see himself and the strategy of development, to live with

the pain of many, to work with such qualities as cooperation, solidarity, creativity, humanity, nobility, to be a mature owner of his field, to have high professional competence, to be experienced. A leader must be sincere in his interactions with his team, be successful in his work, correctly analyze various problematic situations and conflicts, be thoughtful, broad-minded, and creative [8, p. 35-42].

The uniqueness of the management of educational institutions is the adaptation of the management of the educational institution to internal and external changes, the rational use of leadership styles, the mastery and application of management principles, the determination of management based on the direction of the development and improvement of the activities of the educational institution, as well as the information that is of great importance in the performance of tasks in the direction of achieving the specified goal. It is expressed more clearly in the process of implementation of the functions of analysis, goal-motivation, foresight-planning, organization-execution, control-diagnosis and regulation-coordination, and it is directed to the organization of the educational process on a scientific basis, to ensure its effectiveness, and to improve the activities of the educational institution. In the implementation of these functions, the leaders' adherence to democratic principles, the involvement of all employees in the management process, has an effect on achieving high efficiency.

The teacher's organization is based on innovative approaches and expresses his competence in the direction of organizational competence. Organizational competence is understood as the teacher's psychological-pedagogical worldview and organizational potential, his professional competence and potential. Russian pedagogical scientist A.K. Makarov defines competence as the basis of professional training of the organizer, and distinguishes two directions, that is, professional and personal competence in a certain field. The first is maturity in acquiring professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, and the second is related to a number of necessary universal human qualities [9, p. 786-790] is manifested in reaching.

Organizational competence manifests itself in the form of values, generally accepted beliefs, and existing norms of behavior that are based on relationships within and outside the educational institution. It is a priority task of the state policy to create opportunities for every citizen of the country to get an education, to become a necessary specialist in the future, and to demonstrate their existing worldly knowledge in practice. Another of the main directions of the state policy is the continuous attention to self-development of the individual, continuous education, in accordance with the requirements of the information society, innovative development [10, p. 6].

As a result of the ongoing democratic reforms, fundamental changes have taken place in the social sphere, an educational system based on an innovative system is being formed, and a new stage of training of qualified personnel has been entered. came into use as

In the development of any society, in the implementation of economic, political and spiritual reforms of social life, the attitude of the population to work and their professional skills are the factors that determine the speed of the country's development. These formed qualities and character have an important place in solving the moral standard, in particular the issue of competence, in the organized activity. The organizational competence of the teacher depends on his initiative and responsibility. The organizer directs not only the personality of the pedagogue, but also the students he teaches or the organizational activities he manages towards creativity. In our opinion, the spirituality and moral image of the pedagogue in social development can be conditionally divided into the following:

Firstly, spiritually - it plays a fundamental role in the morals of a person. It is considered that the level of spiritual image is not high. This is of great importance at the time of social reforms. The reason is that it is natural to have various difficulties. A person needs patience along with patience to overcome difficulties. In place of patience, it is necessary to direct the individual's will to his thinking, experience and knowledge to solve problems. The organizing pedagogue allows to work conscientiously by showing initiative with the will of his team, to coordinate the interests of the society with the interests of the team. This determines the organizational potential of the organizing pedagogue, as well as his moral character and spiritual qualities. The teacher's moral outlook determines his level of humanity. The characteristics of this pedagogue, such as conscientiousness and will, occupy an important place. The teacher's qualities of conscientiousness make it possible to control the important elements of his spiritual and moral worldview in his work and self. Organizational competence of pedagogues-students will be conscientious and morally important in terms of pedagogical foundations. At the same time, the work qualities of pedagogues-students can be evaluated not as an additional, but as an important profession. His initiative, enthusiasm in the work team, self-sacrifice are the reasons for the rise of his team. The spiritual image of the pedagogue-listeners and their moral qualities ensure that they are in direct harmony with the psyche of the pedagogue. This represents the social status of the qualities of courage and will.

Secondly, the hard work of pedagogues depends on the leadership skills of creating an atmosphere of hard work in the team. Only a leader with high human qualities can be a master of this art and thereby achieve high results in work, leave a bright mark and a good name in life. [11, p. 97]

In this case, the pedagogue's hard work along with moral qualities and the leader's motivation to the team is the key to effectiveness. Hard work is a process that ensures the productivity of a person both qualitatively and quantitatively. In this process, the pedagogue's attitude to work is positive, and his enthusiasm in the work process is manifested in an energetic form. If the organizing pedagogues' diligence in the team is not unique, it can demand hard work from the listeners

In conclusion, it should be noted that a sense of responsibility is the most necessary moral quality for a pedagogue. In this regard, individuals are generally responsible for their activities and duties, while the pedagogue considered that teachers are responsible for their team. The concept of duty and responsibility are very close to each other, where duty requires moral standards. Responsibility is the feeling of responsibility for the fulfillment or non-fulfilment of this duty.

Pedagogical foundations of the organizational competence of the listeners depend on the situations of responsibility for their task, which are relevant for the responsibility of the organizing pedagogue. In our opinion, these include:

1. The student's ability or inability to meet social and moral requirements is studied.
2. Pupils' awareness and understanding of their activity in the social process.
3. Lack of capacity and capacity for responsibility.
4. Responsibility in the organizational competence of the teacher.
5. Increasing the social activity of pedagogues in the socio-political life of society. It is necessary to take into account the possibilities of the whole team

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